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Dangers Brought by using AI

Can the truth survive in an era where AI can effortlessly impersonate anyone to spread and making false information? Artificial Intelligence, in short AI, has been taking over our social media in this era, but where and when are we going to draw the line? When are we going to see that AI can be used to impersonate people and might be used to steal people's identities to spread false information? By what means can we identify the facts? This is particularly true for the elderly, who are often more trusting, especially when they see a familiar face, whether it belongs to a celebrity or an ordinary person. Also, to the millennials who are easily persuaded by AI-generated information posted on various social media platforms.

In the digital age, technology is part of our daily lives. However, then suddenly, artificial intelligence (AI) emerged. At first, AI was used as an assistant to provide in-depth explanations of what students were looking for, but some apps use AI to create videos or clips using people's faces. What started as a joke is now used to create videos that may spread false information. It is not far in the future that AI may be used to impersonate different individuals to fool and gain money from older populations, as they are more likely to believe everything they see on social media. AI platforms can also be used to create videos about medicines that, instead of helping individuals be informed about different diseases, spread false information about medicines, especially herbal medicines. In this generation, AI has become increasingly alarming. There was even a post circulating on social media featuring an image claiming that there would be no power supply for three months. However, this is entirely false, it was nothing more than AI-generated content. Countless people fell for the hoax, but others remained skeptical and recognized right away that it was AI-generated.

To conclude, users must be observant on social media due to the spread of fake news. Some people who can easily distinguish AI from real videos, consisting of real people, can help individuals properly distinguish between Artificial intelligence and real videos. The public must be informed about how to avoid being easily fooled by videos created by these platforms, to avoid scams and false information. There are so many programs and campaigns that can help individuals identify AI-generated false content and verify facts to separate truth from misinformation.